

Magic Healing Water with Simple and Cheap Methods

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Abstract:- Almost everyone has been sick and in this modern era, every disease attacks a person tends to also using modern therapeutic treatments and the use of chemical drugs, treatment with this will cost a lot of money and tend to have side effects. However, in the midst of this modern era, everyone, various groups and everywhere can use a simple, easy and inexpensive treatment method, namely using water therapy. Water can be found anywhere very easily and it turns out that water can be used as a healing therapy for various diseases. This research was conducted with a qualitative method by collecting various sources of book libraries and online media. This research is expected to be used as a means of helping everyone to do healing therapy from disease using a simple method, namely water.

Keywords:- Water, Cheap, Medicine, Miracle Healer, Simple.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is a medium that is easy to find because it is close to its existence and its use is always related to human daily life. The need for water is the most basic need in human life, especially drinking water. The human body must always consume water. "Drinking water is one of the most important things in human life, especially in the health sector. Without drinking water regularly, the human body will become dehydrated. Not only that, the human body can also be easily attacked by other diseases caused by lack of fluids in the body."¹

"In daily activities, humans need energy from food and drink to maintain their survival. Humans cannot survive without drinking, because in general 70-80% of the human body consists of water, especially the brain and blood, so humans cannot live without water. This understanding is often not known by everyone, so the mistake that often occurs is the habit of drinking water only when thirsty. This results in the expenditure and intake of water that occurs in the human body is not balanced. This incident can later cause a person to become dehydrated."²

"Utilization of water for human survival is not just to fulfill daily needs in carrying out general activities, such as drinking, bathing, and others. Water turns out to have a very

important role for life processes that exist and occur in the human body. The water content in the human body is much greater than the content of other substances."³

"Human awareness of the importance of the role of water in their lives is increasing. There have been many studies conducted by experts related to water which resulted in various findings on the use of water for humans. One of the findings that has developed and is popular today is that water is one of the best medicines to cure various diseases. Water was able to provide a treatment effect on various types of human diseases. A person with kidney stones, for example, is advised by a doctor to consume lots of water. Dengue fever, diarrhea, high blood pressure, and other diseases are also advised to drink lots of water."⁴

"Water is one of the vital needs for humans so that its function cannot be replaced by other compounds, especially as drinking water. This is very important because the human body really needs water. Almost 70-80% of the human body needs water and contains water. If the body lacks water, humans will become dehydrated. Therefore, it is highly recommended for humans to consume drinking water, especially water on a regular basis."⁵

"The need for water in the human body can increase under certain conditions, for example in a state of fever, physical exercise, and high environmental temperatures where humans will feel thirsty in the hypothalamus. Someone who is in a cold environment tends not to need a lot of drinking water because they don't feel thirsty, so they are reluctant to drink a lot of water. Opinions like this are said to be wrong if they only drink water when they are thirsty. In a cold environment, humans tend to excrete more fluids through urine and breathing, so humans are encouraged to consume more drinking water even though they do not feel thirsty. In addition, consuming drinking water can help us to keep the skin from becoming dry. A person's water needs will also increase when in a fever condition, especially the increased need for water in breathing. This indicates that humans must consume drinking water not only when thirsty, humans must consume drinking water at all times according to the dose notified by

³ Sri RijatiWardiani and DjarlisGunawan, "AKTUALISASI BUDAYA TERAPI AIR SEBAGAI MEDIA PENGOBATAN OLEH JAMAAH DI PESANTREN SURYALAYA – PAGERAGEUNG TASIKMALAYA," *Dharmakarya* 6, no. 1 (2017): 33–39, accessed December 19, 2021, <http://jurnal.unpad.ac.id/dharmakarya/article/view/14852>.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Putri and Fuadah, "Manfaat Air MinumBagi Kesehatan PesertaDidik Pada Tingkat MI/SD."

¹ Nadya Prameski Putri and Dan Anis Fuadah, "Manfaat Air MinumBagi Kesehatan PesertaDidik Pada Tingkat MI/SD," *Al-Adzka: Jurnalllmiah Pendidikan Guru Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* 10, no. 1 (June 9, 2020): 33–42, accessed December 19, 2021, <http://jurnal.uin-antasari.ac.id/index.php/adzka/article/view/3622>.

² Ibid.

the Ministry of Health so that dehydration and other disease disorders do not occur.”⁶

“Water is the second most important natural resource for living things after oxygen. At least 80% of the body consists of fluids (water). According to several experts in their research that at least 95% of the human brain is composed of water, 82% of water is in the blood, 75% of water is in the heart, 86% is in the lungs, and approximately 83% of water is in the kidneys. This is the main factor that causes water to be more important than any other nutrient in the body of living things. One of them is humans are living creatures that will be able to survive for quite a long time even without food intake, but without water humans will not be able to survive. Therefore, God's most perfect creature really needs an adequate supply of water for his health.”⁷

II. METHODS

This study used a qualitative method of literature study. Researchers, trying to answer research problems by looking for sources of literature that are correlated with the research problem. These sources are from books, journals, and other online media. The method used in this research is literature, which is to get information on healing various diseases using a simple therapy, namely water. Then the research is associated with considering the related literature data and analyzing it as a descriptive factual finding.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. THE BENEFITS OF WATER FOR THE HUMAN BODY

a) The vital function of water for the human body

Organs and body tissues are very dependent on the need for water, because our bodies are mostly made up of water. Some of the functions of water that are very vital for the human body, according to Mary in her book, writes the function of water for the body:⁸

- Water is absolutely necessary for efficient blood circulation—because 90% of blood is water. Blood flow carries oxygen and nutrients to all body cells and transports cellular waste to the kidneys, lungs and skin for disposal. The flow also transports white blood cells that fight disease-causing germs in the body.
- Water keeps body temperature normal. Evaporation due to sweating on the skin's surface promotes the reduction of fever.
- Water produces a fluid that constantly moistens the eye. Without tears, the eyes will be dry and red, which interferes with vision, even blindness.

- Water is needed for lubrication (lubrication) and a cushion for bones and joints.
- Water is needed to produce saliva and digestive juices. 6) Water relieves physical and mental fatigue. The brain is made up of almost 85% water. It's no surprise that drinking a glass of water every 10 minutes for an hour can relieve headaches.

If the water supply is lacking in the body, it will have a negative impact on the health of the body, for that the water level in the body must remain normal.

b) Benefits of Using Water in the Human Body

“Drinking lots of water improves the function of the mucous membranes in the intestinal tract. This important cleansing organ, when it gets a lot of water, drains more fluid into the intestines. Thus, comfortable transport increases and helps prevent a universal problem—constipation. This membrane also removes waste materials from the blood, causing the blood to be cleaner in order to build tissues. In this way, water helps both waste removal and network repair.”⁹

c) Benefits of Using Water Outside the Human Body

“All this has to do with water entering the body, but what are the benefits of using water outside of our body? Bathing does more than just cleanse the skin. A warm bath calms nerves and balances blood circulation. Warm baths also make breathing easier, overcoming blockages in the system. Hot showers also benefit the organs of the kidneys and urinary tract. The muscles become more flexible, the body and mind become fitter, the intellect becomes brighter and every faculty comes alive. The above is especially true if a hot or warm bath is followed by use of cold or cool water. The water doesn't need to be so cold that the body gets a shock, but the water temperature needs to be different so the skin can react to the difference.”¹⁰

“Water should not be replaced with other fluids such as fruit juice, milk, tea, coffee, or alcoholic beverages, because these drinks have diuretic properties, namely compounds that increase the flow of urine, so the lost fluid must be replaced so as not to become dehydrated. Dehydration is one of the effects of a lack of drinking water, in addition to other effects, namely shortness of breath, damage to nerve cells, constipation, headaches, stroke, and kidney failure.”¹¹

⁶ Ibid.

⁷SiskaKusumawardani et al., “ANALISIS KONSUMSI AIR PUTIH TERHADAP KONSENTRASI,” *JurnalHolistika* 4, no. 2 (November 25, 2020): 91–95, accessed December 19, 2021, <https://jurnal.umj.ac.id/index.php/holistika/article/view/8128>.

⁸ M.D. Mary Ann McNeilus, *JALAN KESEMBUHAN DARI ALLAH*, 8th ed. (Whalan, MN 55949 USA: Mercy Valley Farm RR1 Box 73, 2001), 33–34.

⁹ Celeste Lee, *MEMAHAMI ORGAN-ORGAN TUBUH & DELAPAN HUKUM KESEHATAN* (Brushton, New York: TEACH Services, Inc., 1997), 193.

¹⁰ Ibid., 194–195.

¹¹Hubungan I Tingkat PengetahuanTentangManfaatMinum Air PutihDenganJumlahKonsumsiMinum AirPutih Dan Pola Penyakit Pada SiswaSmp Negeri KecamatanAlalak and HjNoorhayatiMaslani, “Hubungan Tingkat PengetahuanTentangManfaatMinum Air PutihDenganJumlahKonsumsiMinum AirPutih Dan Pola

"Human awareness of the importance of the role of water in their lives is increasing. There have been many studies conducted by experts related to water which resulted in various findings on the use of water for humans. One of the findings that has developed and is popular today is that water is one of the best medicines to cure various diseases. Water was able to provide a treatment effect on various types of human diseases. A person with kidney stones, for example, is advised by a doctor to consume lots of water. Dengue fever, diarrhea, high blood pressure, and other diseases are also advised to drink lots of water."¹²Mary also lists some of the uses of water outside the human body through a warm bath, including: "protects against colds and other ailments, improves blood circulation, energizes the body, refreshes the mind—increases intelligence and calms nerves, increases muscle flexibility, helps the digestive organs—stomach, liver and intestines."¹³By realizing the importance of water in human life, everyone must use it properly and maximally for the sake of maintaining a healthy and quality life.

B. USING WATER IN RELIEFING SYMPTOMS OF VARIOUS DISEASES *Headaches*

Headaches are often experienced by some people, this may be a symptom that arises as a result of holding back diseases that exist in a person's body. The easiest and cheapest way to relieve headaches can be to use water. Below are some opinions from various magazines or online articles on the benefits of water in relieving headaches.

"Researchers from the University of Maastricht in the Netherlands, suggested that drinking 7 glasses of water a day was able to relieve pain and improve the quality of life of patients frequent headaches. The results showed that participants who were asked to drink water showed a significant reduction in pain due to frequent headaches. Dr. Mark Spigt and his team involved more than 100 patients who often experienced mild to severe headaches. Then the researchers asked half of the participants to drink 1.5 liters of water per day for three months, more than the participants' normal intake of water to relieve discomfort from headaches."¹⁴

Penyakit Pada Siswa Smp Negeri iKecamatan Alalak Tahun 2016," *Jurnal Skala Kesehatan* 8, no. 1 (January 2, 2017), accessed December 19, 2021, <http://www.ejournalskalakesehatan-poltekkesbjm.com/index.php/JSK/article/view/203>.

¹²Wardiani and Gunawan, "AKTUALISASI BUDAYA TERAPI AIR SEBAGAI MEDIA PENGobatan OLEH JAMAAH DI PESANTREN SURYALAYA – PAGERAGEUNG TASIKMALAYA."

¹³Mary Ann McNeilus, *JALAN KESEMBUHAN DARI ALLAH*, 38.

¹⁴"Rutin Minum Air Putih Redakan Sakit Kepala Dan Migrain," accessed December 21, 2021, <https://health.detik.com/hidup-sehat-detikhealth/d-1991687/rutin-minum-air-putih-redakan-sakit-kepala-dan-migrain>.

"Another study published in Nutrition Review found that drinking water relieves headache symptoms in most people who are dehydrated within 30 minutes to three hours. This is why it is important to drink enough water and eat water-rich foods to meet the daily needs of the body."¹⁵

"Headaches happen. The good news is that there are some simple things you can do to ease the pain without going to the doctor or drug store. Try these tips and get a feeling faster: If you have migraines, put a cold compress on your forehead. An ice cube wrapped in a towel, a bag of frozen peas, or even a cold shower can ease the pain. Keep the compress on your head for 15 minutes, then rest for 15 minutes. If you have a tension headache, place a heating pad on your neck or the back of your head. If you have a sinus headache, hold a warm cloth over the painful area. A warm bath might also be helpful."¹⁶

"For those of you who want to cure headaches due to muscle contractions, stress, anxiety or lack of sleep, dip a washcloth in hot water, wring it out, then fold it and place it on the forehead or the back of the neck to relax tense muscles. Meanwhile, to relieve vascular headaches such as migraines, cluster headaches, or pain related to blood vessels in certain areas of the head, you can use ice. Cold temperatures constrict blood vessels, reducing blood flow, thereby relieving pressure and providing relief to a sore head. A study conducted on 55 migraine patients found that 77 percent of those who put an ice pack on their neck immediately felt relief, making this method one of the most effective natural remedies."¹⁷

a) Obesity

"That drinking water can reduce obesity. Drinking water as much as possible or at least six glasses per day will meet the needs of fiber and fluids. Hydrotherapy can help the process of removing all toxins in the body, including excessive blood sugar levels. Drinking water causes the breakdown of sugar so that to remove chemical substances through the kidneys, large amounts of fluid are needed in one administration in the morning. Consuming water can help get rid of toxic substances in the body, including excess sugar."¹⁸

¹⁵ "15 Cara Menghilangkan Sakit Kepala Tanpa Obat, Perbanyak Minum Air Putih Hingga Berhenti Mengunyah - Halaman All - Tribunnews.Com," accessed December 21, 2021,

<https://www.tribunnews.com/kesehatan/2020/11/29/15-cara-menghilangkan-sakit-kepala-tanpa-obat-perbanyak-minum-air-putih-hingga-berhenti-mengunyah?page=all>.

¹⁶ "10 Cara Hilangkan Sakit Kepala: Anda Wajib Tahu Ini Tips Mudahnya!," accessed December 21, 2021, <https://www.ciputramedicalcenter.com/10-cara-menghilangkan-sakit-kepala/>.

¹⁷ "Usir Sakit Kepala Dengan Cara Mudah Ini - Info Sehat Klikdokter.Com," accessed December 21, 2021, <https://www.klikdokter.com/info-sehat/read/3620809/usir-sakit-kepala-dengan-cara-mudah-ini>.

¹⁸Kusniawati Kusniawati and Parta Suhandha, "HIDROTERAPI DAPAT MENURUNKAN KADAR GULA DARAH SEWAKTU PENDERITA DIABETES

b) Fever

“Fever is the body's natural process to fight infections that enter the body when the body temperature increases beyond normal body temperature ($> 37.2^{\circ}\text{C}$). An increase in body temperature results in fever and is one of the most common manifestations of illness in children.”¹⁹ Although fever is a disease in general and everyone has experienced it but this condition must be handled so that it is not sustainable and has serious effects, “a fever that is not handled properly can cause body temperature to increase and eventually seizures and even potential epilepsy due to brain nerve damage. The incidence of fever in cases of GE in the world according to UNICEF and WHO in 2012, is the number 2 cause of death in children under five, and number 3 in infants. Data from UNICEF shows that 1.5 million children die every year. In Indonesia alone, 460 children under the age of 5 have died.”¹⁹

“Treatment of fever can be in the form of hydrotherapy. Hydrotherapy is the use of water to treat and relieve various ailments in a certain way. There are 2 types of hydrotherapy, namely internal hydrotherapy which includes drinking water, milk, juice and others, while external hydrotherapy includes warm water compresses with plaster compresses, warm water compresses and hibiscus leaf compresses, sponge baths, and *tepid sponge*.”²⁰

“*Hyperthermia* when a child has a fever will cause evaporation of body fluids, causing dehydration, therefore hyperthermia must be handled properly. Non-pharmacological management of hyperthermia is with warm water compresses. There are several compression techniques that can be applied to reduce body temperature, namely a combination of warm compresses with block techniques and wiping techniques (*sponge bath*). A warm compress is an action lowering body temperature by using a cloth or towel that has been dipped in warm water, then affixed to certain body parts so as to create a sense of comfort.”²¹

MELITUS TIPE 2 DI PUSKESMAS CIPONDOH KOTA TANGERANG,” *Jurnal Medikes (Media Informasi Kesehatan)* 4, no. 2 (November 30, 2017): 157–166, accessed December 19, 2021, <https://jurnal.poltekkesbanten.ac.id/Medikes/article/view/82>.

¹⁹RoihatulZahroh, matul A Khasanah Program Studi Ilmu Keperawatan Fakultas Ilmu Kesehatan Universitas Gresik Jl R Hakim No, and B Gresik, “Efektifitas Pemberian Kompres Air Hangat Dan Sponge Bath Terhadap Perubahan Suhu Tubuh Pasien Anak Gastroenteritis,” *JURNAL NERS LENTERA* 5, no. 1 (November 29, 2017): 33–42, accessed December 20, 2021, <http://jurnal.wima.ac.id/index.php/NERS/article/view/1568>.

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹Rastia Irmachatsalihah and Dera Alfiyanti, “Kombinasi Kompres Hangat Dengan Teknik Blok Dan Teknik Seka (Tepid Sponge Bath) Menurunkan Suhu Tubuh

“Giving a warm compress to the large blood vessel area is an attempt to stimulate the *hypothalamic preoptic* to lower body temperature. Warm signals carried by this blood to *hypothalamus* will stimulate the preoptic area resulting in the release of signals by the effector system. This signal will cause more body heat expenditure through two mechanisms, namely dilation of peripheral blood vessels and sweating.”²²

c) Controlling Blood Pressure

“Based on data obtained in 2015, the World Health Organization (WHO) shows that worldwide, around 1.4 billion people or 39.6% of the earth's population suffer from hypertension. This number has continued to increase since 2009 where the number of patients with hypertension found as many as 972 million people or 26.4% with the highest number of sufferers being men, namely 76.6%. In Indonesia every year there are 175,000 deaths due to hypertension and there are 450,000 cases of hypertension, from the hypertension cases it is known that 337,500 cases (75%) are of productive age (15-50 years) which are dominated by men, and 112,500 cases (25%) are undiagnosed and only partially covered in the hypertension disease control program in accordance with WHO recommendations”²⁴ “Hypertension disease continues to increase from year to year. Not only in Indonesia, but also in the world. As many as 1 billion people in the world or 1 in 4 adults suffer from this disease. In fact, it is estimated that the number of people with hypertension will increase to 1.6 billion by 2025.”²³

“Management for tackling hypertension broadly includes 2 types of management, namely pharmacological management and non-pharmacological management. Pharmacological management is using drugs, while non-pharmacological includes herbal therapy, nutrition, progressive relaxation, meditation, laughter,

Pada Anak Penderita Gastroenteritis,” *Ners Muda* 1, no. 3 (December 31, 2020): 193–199, accessed December 20, 2021, <https://jurnal.unimus.ac.id/index.php/nersmuda/article/view/6215>.

²²Fadli and Hasan, “PENGARUH KOMPRES HANGAT TERHADAP PERUBAHAN SUHU TUBUH PADA PASIEN FEBRIS.”

²³Erika Untari Dewi, “PENGARUH TERAPI RENDAM KAKI AIR HANGAT TERHADAP PERUBAHAN TEKANAN DARAH PADA PENDERITA HIPERTENSI DI RT 7 RW 5 KELURAHAN WONOTETO KECAMATAN WONOKROMO SURABAYA,” *Jurnal Keperawatan* 5, no. 2 (October 3, 2016): 7 Pages-7 Pages, accessed December 20, 2021, <https://jurnal.stikeswilliambooth.ac.id/index.php/d3kep/article/view/50>.

acupuncture, acupressure, aromatherapy and warm water therapy.”²⁴

“One of the efforts that can be done to reduce or control blood pressure is hydrotherapy (hydrotherapy). This treatment is a treatment without side effects. Hydrotherapy has a good impact on the whole body. This is triggered by the release of the endorphins system in the body. Hydrotherapy is a method of treatment and healing by using water to get a therapeutic or healing effect. The use of water therapy in question is drinking 1.5 liters of water every morning immediately after waking up. Consuming water can reduce high blood pressure because water can dissolve excess salt so that it is wasted with urine. Physiologically it is explained that the mechanism of action of the *Renin Angiotensin-Aldosterone* (RAAS) system, *Angiotensin* to maintain or increase the volume of extracellular fluid is carried out through increasing water and sodium intake.”²⁵

“The results showed that before being given warm water therapy, the average respondent's systolic blood pressure was 170 mmHg and after being given therapy it was 155.36 mmHg with a difference in the average value of 14,643 mmHg. Looking at the average systolic blood pressure before and after being given warm water therapy, it shows that there is a significant difference between blood pressure before and after giving warm water therapy.”²⁶

“Warm water therapy is a type of natural therapy that aims to increase blood circulation, increase muscle relaxation, nourish the heart, relax muscles, relieve stress, relieve muscle stiffness, muscle pain, relieve pain, increase capillary permeability, provide warmth to the body. body so it is very useful for blood pressure lowering therapy in hypertension.”²⁷

“Improved blood circulation also facilitates lymph circulation so that it cleanses the body of toxins. Therefore people suffering from diseases such as rheumatism, arthritis, sciatica, backache,

insomnia, fatigue, stress, poor blood circulation (hypertension), muscle aches, cramps, stiffness, water therapy can be used to relieve these problems.”²⁸

“Based on the results of a case study regarding the application of foot bath therapy using warm water in lowering blood pressure in clients with hypertension, it can be concluded that the implementation of foot soak therapy resulted in a decrease in blood pressure after therapy 1 time for three days.”²⁹

d) Lowering Blood Sugar Levels

“The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that in 2025 it is estimated that the number of people with diabetes over 20 years old will increase to 300 million people. Diabetes cases will increase to 42% from 51-72 million people in developed countries and increase by 170% from 84-228 million people in developing countries. The mortality rate associated with type 2 diabetes is around 3.2 million and at least one in 10 adult deaths (35-64 years) is associated with type 2 diabetes. DM cases after India, China and the United States.”³⁰

Diabetes Mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by hyperglycemia that occurs due to defects in insulin secretion, insulin action or both (American Diabetes Association / ADA 2005). There are several types of Diabetes Mellitus based on their classification, namely Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM), Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (NIDDM), and Gestational Diabetes Mellitus. Approximately 90%-95% of people with diabetes have type 2 diabetes mellitus. Based on WHO data, type 2 diabetes mellitus has become an epidemic and is one of the health threats in the world.”³¹

²⁴Nazaruddin et al., “PENGARUH TERAPI RENDAM KAKI DENGAN AIR HANGAT TERHADAP PENURUNAN TEKANAN DARAH PENDERITA HIPERTENSI DI WILAYAH KERJA PUSKESMAS POASIA KOTA KENDARI.”

²⁵ Siti Hadrayanti Ananda et al., “Efektivitas Terapi Air Terhadap Penurunan Tekanan Darah Pada Penderita Hipertensi,” *Jurnal Keperawatan* 4, no. 01 (July 31, 2020): 13–17, accessed December 20, 2021, <https://stikesk-kendari.e-journal.id/JK/article/view/233>.

²⁶ Reni Dwi Setyaningsih et al., “PENGARUH PEMBERIAN TERAPI AIR HANGAT TERHADAP PENURUNAN TEKANAN DARAH PADA LANSIA DENGAN HIPERTENSI,” *Viva Medika: Jurnal Kesehatan, Kebidanan dan Keperawatan* 9, no. 1 (2016), accessed December 20, 2021, <https://ejournal.uhb.ac.id/index.php/VM/article/view/297>.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Jurnal Ilmiah Keperawatan Orthopedi et al., “Penerapan Terapi Rendam Kaki Menggunakan Air Hangat Dalam Menurunkan Tekanan Darah,” *JIKO (Jurnal Ilmiah Keperawatan Orthopedi)* 3, no. 2 (July 8, 2019): 74–80, accessed December 20, 2021, <https://ejournal.akperfatmawati.ac.id/index.php/JIKO/article/view/33>.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Kusniawati Kusniawati and Parta Suhandha, “HIDROTERAPI DAPAT MENURUNKAN KADAR GULA DARAH SEWAKTU PENDERITA DIABETES MELITUS TIPE 2 DI PUSKESMAS CIPONDOH KOTA TANGERANG,” *Jurnal Medikes (Media Informasi Kesehatan)* 4, no. 2 (November 30, 2017): 157–166, accessed December 20, 2021, <https://jurnal.poltekkesbanten.ac.id/Medikes/article/view/82>.

³¹ Elmatris Sy et al., “EFEK HIDROTERAPI PADA PENURUNAN KADAR GULA DARAH SESAAT (KGDS) TERHADAP PENDERITA DIABETES MELITUS TIPE 2,” *Majalah Kedokteran Andalas* 36, no. 2 (August 30, 2012): 202–214, accessed December 20, 2021, <http://jurnalmka.fk.unand.ac.id/index.php/art/article/view/128>.

"That hydrotherapy can prevent diabetic ulcers. Hydrotherapy causes the breakdown of sugar which is excreted through urine so that blood sugar levels can be controlled so that complications of diabetic ulcers can be prevented. Hydrotherapy has a positive impact on the body, one of which is lowering blood sugar levels in patients with type 2 diabetes. The results of this study are evidence base practice. for nurses in carrying out nursing actions to overcome patient nursing problems.³⁴ "That drinking water can reduce obesity. Drinking water as much as possible or at least six glasses per day will meet the needs of fiber and fluids. Hydrotherapy can help the process of removing all toxins in the body including excess blood sugar levels."³²

"That with 1.5 liters (1500 cc) of water therapy coupled with oral therapy can reduce blood sugar levels for a moment in Type 2 DM patients. Consuming large amounts of water in the morning after waking up is good. Because in this condition the stomach is empty so that the stomach wall can absorb water quickly, then flowed into the blood, then flowed by the blood to the kidneys and excreted through the urine. The implementation of water therapy for 7 consecutive days is based on the results of research and experience that of several diseases that can be cured with water therapy, one of which is DM for 7 days."³³

e) Dengue fever

"Treatment So far because dengue is a viral disease, there is no treatment to stop or slow down the development of this virus. Treatment can only be done in a symptomatic way, namely eliminating the symptoms seen by each patient. Fluids can be given to reduce dehydration and drugs given to reduce fever, and treat bleeding. Efforts to prevent or overcome a state of shock / preshock, namely by trying to make the patient drink a lot of about 1.5 to 2 liters of water in 24 hours."³⁴

C. WATER THERAPY

a) Hot Water Therapy

"Immersion therapy using warm water with a temperature of 390-400 C can treat hypertension non-pharmacologically by soaking the feet. Scientifically, warm water has a physiological impact on the body, firstly it affects the blood vessels where the warm

water makes blood circulation smooth, stabilizes blood flow and heart work."³⁵

"Researchers assume that giving warm water therapy can relieve stress, anxiety, depression, anxiety and provide mental and emotional fitness as well as make the feeling relaxed, calm and comfortable so that there is a decrease in heart rate. Warm water with a temperature of 370-390 C can relax stiff muscles, dilate blood vessels, and increase the permeability of blood vessels and make blood circulation smoother. A condition where ventricular contractions begin to occur, so that with the dilation of blood vessels, blood flow becomes smooth and able to push blood into the heart so that it can lower systolic blood pressure. "Scientifically warm water has a physiological impact on the body. First, it affects the blood vessels where the warm water makes blood circulation smoother. Second, strengthen the muscles and ligaments that affect the joints of the body. This non-pharmacological alternative therapy uses an easier and cheaper method because it uses warm water that can be done at home."³⁶

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Water is very useful and important for the human body, for that everyone should use it properly. The use of water has many benefits in the human body and outside the body in daily life, it can be said that humans cannot be separated from the use of water. Water is not only used as a daily necessity but can be used to cure or reduce the risk of diseases such as fever, dengue fever, controlling high blood pressure, lowering blood pressure, obesity and headaches. Treatment using water is very simple, cheap and easy to obtain, and most importantly there is no risk of side effects. We should make good use of water as a gift from God for basic human needs and can be used for the restoration of the human body.

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³² Ibid.

³³ Sy et al., "EFEK HIDROTERAPI PADA PENURUNAN KADAR GULA DARAH SESAAT (KGDS) TERHADAP PENDERITA DIABETES MELITUS TIPE 2."

³⁴ Ira Aini Dania, "GAMBARAN PENYAKIT DAN VEKTOR DEMAM BERDARAH DENGUE (DBD)," *Warta Dharmawangsa*, no. 48 (2016): 1829–7463, accessed December 21, 2021, <https://jurnal.dharmawangsa.ac.id/index.php/juwarta/article/view/179>.

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